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**Topic: DYNAMICS OF MATERIAL PERCEPTION BY STUDENTS:
"ACADEMIC MOBILITY" COURSE IN BLENDED LEARNING**

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MASTER'S THESIS ASSIGNMENT

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1. Thesis topic: Dynamics of Material Perception by Students: "Academic Mobility" course in blended learning.

2. Thesis aim: to design a unique online course for students especially university students with B1 English language proficiency combining asynchronous and synchronous instructional modes and targeted at developing English grammar and vocabulary skills.

3. Research materials: designed online course, questionnaire, survey questionnaire, related publications, journals, articles, websites, analyses.

4. The main publications, including:

4.1. Books: VanPatten, B., Keating, G. D., & Wulff, S. S. (2020). *Theories in Second language acquisition: An introduction*. Routledge.

4.2. Research reports, PhD dissertations, bachelor's, and master's theses, etc.: Abdelati, S. (2019). *Communication strategies in Libyan EFL classrooms: Materials, perceptions and practices* (Doctoral dissertation, Sheffield Hallam University).

4.3. Periodicals: Mayer, R. E. (2018). Thirty Years of research on online learning. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, 33(2), 152–159; Anas, A. (2020). Perceptions of Saudi Students to Blended Learning Environments at the University of Bisha, Saudi Arabia. *Arab World English Journal (AWEJ) Special Issue on CALL*, (6). 261-277.

4.4. Reference books and methodological publications (including publications on methods of research data analysis): Council of Europe (2020). *Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, teaching, assessment*. Cambridge University Press.

5. The main research stages and forms of assessable output of each stage: Theoretical stage includes reading and analyzing various relevant sources (analytical review), developing research methodology, conducting and analyzing needs analysis of the course (reading and analyzing relevant education documents as well as conducting needs analysis questionnaire to analyze target audience, proficiency level, learning needs, learning style), planning and organizing to design an online English course (designing course goals and aims, designing syllabus, organizing and designing interactive online materials). An abstract and presentation at the 79th Science Days Conference. Practical stage (conducting research, analyzing results, making conclusions and recommendations): pilot testing of the course "Academic Mobility". Analytical stage: report on the course trial using the data on learners' performance and the survey questionnaire.

6. Equipment and methods to be used in research: content analysis, comparative analysis, course piloting on *Canvas Instructure* LMS, statistical analysis, and survey questionnaire.

7. The use of information technologies in research: The thesis is written in *MS Word*, the research is conducted with the help of *Canvas Instructure* (LMS), various digital tools for content making and *Google* forms for surveys, *MS Excel* and *JASP Statistical analysis* software to analyze data.

8. The approximate list of the main issues to be discussed and analyzed in literature review: material dynamics, multimedia materials, blended learning (synchronous and asynchronous).

9. The approximate list of illustrative materials: The textual part of the research will be accompanied by such material as figures and tables.

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Abstract

The shift from traditional classrooms to online learning has prompted educators to enhance virtual teaching methods, employing technology to create engaging and supportive learning experiences. There are numerous courses designed by educators to facilitate smooth online learning and impact learners with new skills. However, the question is whether these online materials are suitable and appropriate to cater learners needs by incorporating their perspectives on the materials on online learning environment to maximize their learning experience and make it more effective.

This study explores students' perceptions of online course materials and examines the impact of the online course materials on grammar and vocabulary skills improvements for students in the online course titled "Academic Mobility" designed on *Canvas Instructure* focusing on grammar and vocabulary learning skills.

The study adopted a mixed-method design, incorporating survey, grammaticality judgment tests, and vocabulary assessments in pre and posttests. Procedural framework, from need analysis to result reporting, ensured a learner-centered and contextually relevant course design.

The majority favored illustrated text materials, such as PowerPoint, MS Word, and PDF formats, video formats were well-received, while materials illustrated through images, mind maps and text messages were less preferred. Overall, the study revealed a positive perception of the learning materials, including their relevance and quality, which was reflected in the survey responses. Additionally, analysis of the pre and post tests revealed statistically significant improvements in participants' vocabulary and grammar knowledge.

This study contributes valuable insights into the design of effective learning materials within a blended online learning environment and maximize students learning experience in online learning settings.

The thesis consists of 75, includes 10 figures, 11 tables, a list of 43 references, and 3 appendices.

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Introduction

The advancement of science and technology has left a profound impact across various fields, from science, and communication to education. The integration of technology in education has transformed traditional teaching and learning methods into digital learning also known as online learning. This learning approach incorporates several elements such as virtual classrooms, computer, and web-based learning [1]. Recently, online learning is becoming an increasingly popular way for students to have access to education, and it offers flexibility accessibility, and interactive learning experiences for students to learn from anywhere at their own pace. It can take various forms such as web-based courses, self-paced learning courses, and videoconferencing. Online learning is increasingly progressing and drawing more attention since instruction is evolving from traditional means of instructional delivery such as books and in-person classrooms towards web-based content such as instructional videos, podcasts, narrated animations, and hypertexts that incorporate printed texts and illustrations with educational games and simulations [2].

Online venues have provided students with numerous opportunities to further their careers and enhance their experience by acquiring new skills through online courses. These platforms have provided them with numerous innovative ways to facilitate learning; nevertheless, to fully utilize these new opportunities research-based are required [2]. It is obvious and acknowledged that the advancement of instructional technologies has greatly enhanced and elevated e-learning. Online instruction and courses provide opportunities for the development of innovative teaching and learning resources to capture students' attention and foster their interest in learning. For online students, materials are essential resources for them to achieve successful learning outcomes. However, it is crucial to identify the most effective ways to utilize digital technologies to design and provide quality instruction to online students and ensure that the online materials are effective and suitable for them to achieve their desired learning outcomes.

Moreover, online courses have been used to promote and improve English language learning as a foreign or second language. Teachers employ digital tools and Web 2.0 technologies to design learning materials and content that facilitate language learning for their students. This enables teachers to customize classroom activities and improve language learning experiences according to the student's needs. Additionally, teachers and course designers utilize these digital technologies to deliver their learning materials and resources to the students in an innovative, engaging, and interactive way, enhancing the students' language learning process. Online course delivery can occur synchronously, asynchronously, or in a combination of both simply known as blended or bichnonous. Teachers and students have the freedom to select the format that is most supportive for them, and learners can choose to enroll in the format that best suits their needs.

As education continues to embrace digitalization, students have access to a wider range of learning materials and resources that can enhance their understanding and improve their performance. Hence, course designers need to consider the selection and development of suitable instructional materials to maximize the learning outcomes of the students. Consequently, the act of choosing and creating appropriate learning materials for the online environment cannot be successful and effective without considering students' perspectives towards these materials.

Furthermore, in recent years there has been a large number of learning contents and materials developed by various course designers, educators, and experts to foster learning in digital settings. Today, we engage in an exploration of e-learning, where digital innovations offer exceptional opportunities for engagement and growth. Educators and course designers are striving to understand the complex relationship between online course learning materials and their learning outcomes in online learning settings. Therefore, it is essential to assess students' perspectives on the appropriateness and effectiveness of online learning materials to create a more inclusive and impactful learning experience in online learning environments. By understanding how learners interact with diverse learning modalities, we can tailor instructional materials, content, and strategies to optimize engagement and foster

meaningful learning experiences. To achieve this, it is important to explore students' perceptions of online learning material and their impacts on students' learning outcomes. Hence, this study covers the following questions in order to investigate the issue. The *research questions* investigated in this study are:

- How do students perceive various digital learning materials in online learning environment?
- To what extent does the course material impact grammar and vocabulary skills.

Several researchers discovered that the internet is widely available to both language teachers and students. The internet serves as a virtual library, allowing language learners to access authentic materials and other learning resources that are significantly valuable for the development of their language skills [3, p. 612]. Through the use of various web resources such as online texts and articles, videos, podcasts, audiovisual materials, and interactive exercises, students can improve their language skills including grammar, vocabulary, speaking, reading, listening, and writing skills in a more meaningful way. For example, grammar and vocabulary courses and activities such as quizzes, exercises, and tests can help students practice and reinforce what they have learned. Online materials and resources help students to immerse themselves in the target language and advance their proficiency in a more engaging and interactive way. Hence, as technology advances language course developers must design suitable materials and resources to create dynamic and effective learning environments for the students. Therefore, course developers need to examine the effectiveness of their online materials and resources by assessing how online students perceive them and how they impact their learning experiences.

This paper *aims* to examine and investigate the dynamics of material perception by students in an online learning environment through the online blended course designed on *Canvas Instructure*. Learning materials play a crucial role in the teaching and learning process. They consist of students' activities, content, topic materials, samples, assessments, learning outcomes, and helping students to achieve their learning goals and objectives.

The purpose of this study is defined by several *objectives* to be achieved including:

- to analyze the significance of digital learning and the way language teachers can incorporate digital technology in course design.
- to analyze the ways students can perceive online materials and resources as well as their impact on students' learning outcomes.
- to design a course based on the needs analysis.
- to investigate students' perception of online learning materials in the designed blended course.
- to test the effectiveness of the digital course on learning grammar and vocabulary skills.
- to work out recommendations for further course improvement based on study results and learners' performance.

When it comes to online course materials creation, developers need to adhere to certain principles as proposed by [4]. Those principles such as materials should facilitate student self-investment and achieve their learning impact. Additionally, course designers should acknowledge that students differ in learning styles, so the materials should consider these differences in learning styles, affective attitudes, and learning goals. The developers must first determine learners' needs, then assess the students' needs and gather the appropriate instructional materials according to their needs and learning goals. After that, identify potential techniques and approaches that may be implemented as well as consider their learning styles [1; 5]. Furthermore, when creating online materials, designers should not only consider the above-mentioned principles but also follow the practical guidelines throughout the process. For instance, using videos, text-based materials, presentation tools, web pages on the internet, hyperlinking, video format virtual classrooms, and communication tools to enhance learning.

The aforementioned principles are important to consider when planning the digital course. Therefore, recognizing the importance of these principles, the course used in this study is created based on a thorough need analysis conducted prior to its

development. This analysis aimed to determine the student's needs, preferred learning styles, motivational levels, and learning objectives to tailor the learning materials and resources to suit their requirements. The need analysis results to the course development in *Canvas Instructure*. The course delivery format is through a blended learning style (synchronous and asynchronous), as proposed by the students while conducting need analysis. This format as requested by the students provides them with an opportunity to interact with the teacher and practice what they learn in the virtual classroom and an opportunity for them to share their views with other students in virtual environment.

The unique aspect of this research lies in the fact that instead of exploring students' material perception and its impact in online learning settings using the pre-existing online courses as most researchers do, this study involve course development specifically for the target audience. Additionally, it highlights the benefit of conducting need analysis before designing the course, something that is overlooked by most of the course developers especially in the recent digital age where learners have diverse learning needs and expectations.

This study is *significant* to language course developers as it provides them with valuable insights on how to create effective and engaging online courses that cater to students' preferences and needs. On top of that, it informs them about the best practices for instructional methodologies and material formats in course design, with a focus on creating inclusive and impactful learning experiences in digital environments. Overall, this study is valuable for designers to improve their courses and provide students with appropriate learning instructions and effective learning experiences in online settings.

1 Theoretical Justification of the Course Design

This chapter is dedicated to providing a theoretical justification of the online course design titled “Academic Mobility” which aims to enhance students’ vocabulary and grammar skills. The chapter is divided into two main parts: the first part conducts a thorough examination of existing literature and other theoretical sources concerning material design in digital learning environments, while the second part presents analysis of learning management systems, a comprehensive needs analysis, and other essential components for designing and implementing the online course in digital settings.

1.1 Analytical Literature Review

The contemporary landscape of education has undergone a profound transformation with the integration of technology, giving rise to innovative modes of instructional delivery, with online courses becoming a prominent feature in academic settings. Blended online learning (bichronous), this mixed instructional approach, combining virtual teaching with digital components, has sparked a growing interest in understanding the intricate dynamics that shape students’ perception of course materials within this evolving learning environment. It is vital to select and develop course materials and activities that allow students to discover, explore, and improve their skills and knowledge [6]. In another study conducted by Gilbert discovered that asynchronous learning influences meaningful learning experiences to students through participating in the online discussions and engage with the course content. However, it revealed some drawbacks when it comes to the interaction. The study suggested that asynchronous online discussions are beneficial for online learning when are guided by the instructor [7]. This allows students to have more in-depth understanding of the content materials and discussions to deepen their understanding of the subject matter. Several researchers that examined the effectiveness of the internet and web-based language learning materials found that

they create a self-directed, student-centered, encouraging, and conducive learning environment to the learners.

Blended learning (BL) in other words bichronous learning is a pedagogical approach that has its origin in the development of educational technology and digital learning [8, p. 263). There is no single definition that all educators can agree on the concept of BL in this digital era. It may include a variety of learning context like online environment, virtual classroom, or a combination of both. Bichronous online teaching and learning focuses on the intentional blending of synchronous and asynchronous components to creative novel learning sequence and methods beyond of what can be accomplished with a single method [9]. This learning method is seen as a balanced approach which offer flexibility with asynchronous and real-time interaction in synchronous sessions, creating joyful medium for student engagement [1]. A recent study in meta-analysis found it is beneficial incorporating both synchronous and asynchronous modes of learning rather than relying solely on the use asynchronous learning [10; 11]. The study suggested that it would be beneficial for instructors to include synchronous online meetings on their courses as it offers interactive and significantly lessons. MOOC claims that certain pedagogical attributes such as learning customization, flexibility, active learning, student management, and feedback can be achieved through BL (8, p. 265). For instance, students may use smartphones to record and present data for their project work or may use virtual simulation using their devices to prepare for a practical session. These examples highlight the way the use of technology enhances the learning process by providing interactivity, accessibility, flexibility, and personalization (8, p. 265).

As the internet become more rapidly accessible, educators have extended the utilization of online language learning materials and resources and course delivery approaches [12; 13; 14]. Most educators develop online courses to impact learners with new experiences and skills such as language learning to enhance learners' language acquisition process. Moreover, when creating an online course, it is essential to assess the suitability and appropriateness of the learning materials to be

utilized in the course to ensure it caters students' needs and maximize their learning experience. Additionally, it is significant to consider students' perspectives and preferences on the choice of the course materials that reflect their expectations. in the course. This can help to enhance learner satisfaction and motivation, ultimately leading to more successful online learning experience.

Perception is a dynamic that occurs in an individual when receives a stimulus from his environment [15, p. 239] Students' perceptions learning materials will affect student learning processes, namely in positive learning. If students have a positive or good perception of the materials, then students will have a good or positive motivation to learn, so the learning process will also be good, and vice versa [15, p. 239]. Perception objective is something that involve others and is not limited to what can be seen in theory [16]. When designing an online course, it is crucial to consider the preferences and viewpoints of learners to ensure that the learning experience for them is both successful and impactful [17]. Preference of the learner is related to the readiness or willingness of the learner to participate in collaborative learning and the factors influencing the readiness for online learning [18]. The prioritization of appropriateness of the course components, clarity, and relevance of the course by the developers as suggested by [19], can create a more favorable and appealing course from the students' perspectives as are the ones who engage with the designed course materials. They highlighted the significance of incorporating the students' perspectives into the course design development. Also, [20; 21] proposed that online instructional formats can achieve similar levels of effectiveness as face-to-face delivery when the appropriate approaches of material delivery are implemented.

Several researchers have conducted studies concerning online courses, but there are few studies conducted to assess materials perception by students in online learning environment. Most studies aim to assess the effectiveness and efficiency of online learning in general, but not in material perception by learners. Hence, this study aims to contribute to the existing studies by conducting a thorough research

that delve into the dynamics of material perception among students through the designed blended online course titled “Academic Mobility”.

By analyzing existing research, this review endeavors to provide a comprehensive understanding of how students perceive and interact with online course materials, thereby contributing valuable insights to the ongoing discourse on effective digital learning methodologies. Several researchers reported variations of the outcomes of students’ perceptions on the learning materials.

In the study conducted by [8], provided an insightful revelation emerged concerning material preferences of learners in the context of blended online courses. The researcher used four kinds of learning materials format to deliver course content on *Blackboard* learning management system (LMS). Learners were asked to choose their preferences on the materials categorized into illustrated materials including MS Word, PDF, and PowerPoint, watching videos, listening to lectures in audio files, and when concepts are illustrated with concepts and images. According to the findings, learners prefer illustrated text materials (MS Word, PDF, and PowerPoint materials) over plain text, video format and audio materials (8, p. 261). Anas's findings highlighted the significance of visual elements in enhancing comprehension and retention, emphasizing the need for tailored approaches to material presentation. On the other hand, result revealed that the least preferred format is audio materials. This preference sheds light on the understanding dynamics that influence students' material perception and engagement within the blended online learning environment. While Anas's work provides a crucial foundation, a comprehensive synthesis of recent studies addressing the broader spectrum of material perception in online courses is notably sparse.

Moreover, according to [22; 23] it is surprisingly that video materials seemed to be more popular among the students, yet illustrated materials were more preferred over the video materials. The study suggested that video materials are more popular as are widely used in digital content in the context of digital learning in India, while dual coded and visual resources receive less attention. Additionally, *YouTube* video materials provide better learning experience to students than watching it directly

from the LMS where the course is designed. The result suggests that to enhance accessibility and students' engagement in learning materials, the selection of learning platform should be considered as it plays a crucial role for students to prefer a certain type of learning materials.

This is contrary to [8] in which the findings suggested that illustrated materials are more preferred to video materials. Even though video materials are more popular in India, but in this study were more less preferred compared illustrated materials. This finding suggest that sometimes certain kind of materials can be popular yet not preferred depending on the platform where the materials are presented.

In addition, there was another study conducted in India. Researchers aimed to assess students' perceptions concerning online learning environment in a broader context. The study revealed that Students preferred well-structured content with recorded videos uploaded in the school website. In order to optimize the learning experience, they further highlighted the significance of quizzes and assignments at the end of each lesson [18, p. 9]. Also, the results revealed that the students had a positive impression towards online learning. These results differ from the previous study conducted by [22; 23] that found that students prefer illustrated materials to video materials despite being popular in India. These results suggest that course designers have to reconsider the selection of learning platform, the inclusion of more video materials, engaging, and interactive activities while designing online courses to enhance students' online learning experience.

Furthermore, [15] conducted studies on synchronous and asynchronous learning concerning students' perception towards synchronous and asynchronous learning, learning platforms, learning materials, and learning activities in various online courses from two different institutions in English language learning. In this study researchers aimed to assess students online learning perceptions on the modes of instructions and material delivery to the students. Regarding materials perception by students on their designed online course, which is the main focus of this study, the finds revealed that students were excited to learn the materials synchronously compared to asynchronously. This meant that most students were fired up in learning

the materials from their lecturers synchronously. Lecturers' explanation about learning materials in synchronous learning platform was seemed to provide better comprehension of the materials to the students. Additionally, learning materials delivered by the lecturers in synchronous learning platforms were easily understood by the students. Yet, the researchers agree that combining synchronous and asynchronous learning was a prominent choice to help students understand materials better and let them get involved in learning activities actively with their classmates. This means that to make students more engaged and motivated in online learning and for them to have a positive perception towards learning materials there is a need use blended learning technique to deliver those materials to the students.

Several studies focus on materials perception by students reported positive feedback on the language learners particularly learning materials motivate them to learn since they can access materials in different formats and attempt the activities at their own pace. For instance, [17] study revealed that majority of the students were motivated to engage with internet -based online resources even if it was not for the purpose of the assessment. Nevertheless, there are still many areas that could be covered when it comes to studying the perception of language learners.

Furthermore, [1] conducted a research to assess students' perception towards English online learning materials. The study aimed to assess how students perceive online learning in terms of materials and its delivery. The result revealed that students indicated that online materials differ from physical classes materials. They suggested that online learning materials are varied, and the tasks and activities assigned by teachers are diverse [1, p. 25]. They also added that online learning materials provided by teachers foster students' independent learning. This means that, the provided materials helped students to understand topics and the subject matter on their own without teachers' intervention on the learning process.

However, they also admitted that the learning materials used in online lessons are found to be more difficult than the face-to-face learning materials. Even though they claimed that the integrated additional online materials from various sources on the internet to be difficulty, they discovered that online learning offers students with

new knowledge and deepens students' understanding of the topics. Hence, they considered it as a new source of learning new language skills and enhance their learning experience. Additionally, based on multimedia the study showed that students were neutral to the audio, video, illustrative, texts-based, Word or PDF material presentation, and visualizations utilized on the course.

Several researchers have conducted studies concerning online course in this era of the advancement of technology- based learning, but there are few studies conducted to assess materials perception by students in online learning environments. Most studies focus on assessing the effectiveness and efficiency of online learning as a whole, but not in material perception by learners. This resulted to the limited number of empirical research concerning student perspectives on online learning materials to facilitate and improve their learning experience. Hence, this study aims to contribute to the existing studies by conducting thorough research that delves into the dynamics of material perception among students through the designed blended online course titled “Academic Mobility”.

Based on the literature review and the gap identified above, in this study the following research questions are going to be addressed.

- How do students perceive various digital learning materials in an online learning environment?
- To what extent does the course impact student's grammar and vocabulary skills?

1.2 Analysis of the Learning Management System (LMS)

The contemporary landscape of education has witnessed a paradigm shift towards online learning in the framework of EFL. Online learning has grown in popularity and requires utilization of technological tools and innovative strategies to organize an effective learning process that meets the demands of students. As the demand for education in the digital age has increased, distinctive and effective e-

learning platforms usually referred to as “Learning Management Systems (LMSs)” are incorporated to facilitate learning process.

Learning Management System is a software application designed to help educators deliver educational courses and training programs, manage documents, grading, and tracking students’ report [15, p. 238]. Learning Management Systems have been specifically developed to ensure users can remain connected remotely and carry out a range of tasks within a single platform. These systems offer students the convenience of studying online without requiring them spend extra time navigating in various of external sites. The use of LMS helps both teachers and students gaining the necessary competencies and communication skills, as well as facilitate interaction, practical collaboration in the real-time with participatory approach to the learning process [15, p. 238]

Whilst there are several specific technologies tailored to provide education on the internet, the majority of the only offer the restricted number of students with a limited feature set within a short free period of time. This prevents users from fully harnessing the learning process. For instance, widely used and popular learning management systems (LMSs) such as *Moodle*, *Canvas*, *Blackboard*, *Edmodo*, and *Google Classrooms* may provide more comprehensive and effective educational tools beyond the limited functionality offered by other platforms.

A comprehensive analysis was carried out to determine the most appropriate Learning Management System (LMS) for designing the course. Several LMSs options were evaluated, including *Google Classroom*, *Canvas Instructure*, and *Moodle*. After careful consideration, *Canvas Instructure* was selected. This decision was made after evaluating a range of features and capabilities offered by different LMSs. This analysis presents a comprehensible evaluation of *Canvas Instructure* based on various criteria and describing its suitability for online learning context.

Accessibility.

Canvas Instructure prioritizes accessibility, ensuring an inclusive online learning environment. It complies with accessibility standards, providing features that accommodate diverse needs, including alt text for images, keyboard navigation,

and compatibility with screen readers. This platform offers a user-friendly interface and is compatible with various devices such as computers, tablets, and smartphones for both iOS and Android devices. Users can access course materials, participate in discussions, submit assignments, complete learning activities, and engage in all LMS activities through their devices promoting flexibility and on-the-go learning. It ensures that learners, including those with disabilities, can easily access and interact with course materials and resources.

Instructors can easily invite learners to join a course by sending email invitations directly through *Canvas Instructure*, offers a flexible approach to learner invitations by providing a code or link sharing option where the platform itself can generate a code or link, which learners can use to self-enroll in the course. This user-friendly feature simplifies the onboarding process, ensuring that learners receive clear instructions to join the course with just a few clicks. Additionally, *Canvas Instructure* offers a choice of navigation language. Users can select their preferred language for navigation, creating a more inclusive and personalized learning experience for individuals whose primary language may not be English.

Course content management.

The effective management of course materials and assignments are crucial for a successful learning experience. *Canvas Instructure* excel in content management as it supports various content types, including text, images, videos, and interactive elements. Its user-friendly interface allows seamless content creation, organization, and delivery. It allows creating and adding materials to the course, supports the incorporation of multimedia elements and allowing students to submit multimedia files as assignments, creating and adding assignments to the course, creating and adding quizzes to the course, allows the organization of materials, assignments, and quizzes into sections or modules, promoting structured learning, uploading files, adding links to external sources, setting time limit for quizzes, setting deadlines for quizzes/tasks, sending announcements, and embedding recourses and other learning materials to the course. Overall *Canvas Instructure* provides a versatile platform for effective course management.

Assessment options.

The use of *Canvas Instructure* provides a robust assessment framework, enabling diverse evaluation methods. Instructors can design quizzes, assignments, and discussions, incorporating multimedia elements for richer assessments. The platform's grading features, including real-time feedback where instructors can provide written comments, annotations on submitted documents, and audio/video feedback. This multifaceted approach facilitates effective communication and ensures that students receive personalized feedback tailored to their work. Both instructors and students benefit from a user-friendly gradebook interface, promoting transparency and accountability.

The feature allowing instructors to easily enter grades, apply rubrics, and access assignment details directly from the gradebook. Students have access to their own personalized gradebook view, allowing them to track their performance throughout the course. All these features available on the platform enhance the assessment process.

Communication tools

Interaction and communication among learners and instructors are crucial in online learning environments. *Canvas Instructure* provides multiple tools to foster effective communication with its suite of collaborative tools. Discussion forums, messaging, video conferencing, and announcements create vibrant classroom dynamic. These tools facilitate peer-to-peer collaboration, questions and answers sessions, and timely communication between instructors and learners, fostering an engaging learning community. *Canvas Instructure* comes equipped with a range of built-in tools that enhance the learning experience. Some notable tools include a calendar for tracking deadlines, a collaborative document editor, and thread reply in discussion forum. These tools foster collaboration, engagement, and ensure a comprehensive learning environment.

To sum up, *Canvas Instructure* is a widely used learning platform for managing and delivering online education, offering a range of tools and features for educational institutions. Its features such as user-friendly interface, strong

capabilities and customization features make it ideal for a variety of online learning environments, including k-12, colleges, and universities. Its comprehensive features include course management, content creation and distribution, assignment and assessment management, communication tools, and analytics to track student progress. *Canvas Instructure* also integrates seamlessly with various learning tools and systems, making it a versatile choice for educators. Its accessibility in different devices particularly in the mobile phones ensures that students and teachers can access their courses and materials on the go. *Canvas Instructure* offers a reliable and comprehensive platform for online learning environment to build and deliver online courses effectively.

2 Description of the Course

This chapter seeks to offer a comprehensive overview of the course “Academic Mobility” focusing on grammar and vocabulary learning designed to equip participants with essential language skills for academic endeavors. By exploring various aspects such as target audience description, needs analysis, course goals and learning objectives, assessment tools, learning activities, and digital tools, it aims to provide a thorough understanding of the course structure and its pedagogical implications. Based on the data gathered essential information on the online course are presented, followed by a justification of the linguistic rationale behind teaching methods and learning materials employed in the course design.

2.1 Target Audience Description

In the process of language learning, grammar and vocabulary are fundamental aspects of language learning, serving as building blocks for effective communication. Grammar provides the structural rules necessary for constructing sentences and organizing thoughts coherently, ensuring clarity and precision in expression. Meanwhile, vocabulary expands learners’ word diversity, enabling them to convey ideas accurately and proficiently across different contexts.

Educators should assess the linguistic needs and proficiency levels of their learners. Understanding the baseline of the language knowledge, such as grammar and vocabulary skills of the target audience. Identifying learners’ specific features helps educators tailor instructional materials and activities to meet specific learning objectives. By aligning instructional strategies with the linguistic needs and proficiency levels of the target audience, educators can optimize learning outcomes and enhance overall language proficiency.

Examining target audience features is crucial in shaping the course design process, as it determines the need for teaching methods, instructional approaches, and materials that cater students’ needs.

The first feature that was reconsidered before designing the course was the learners' language proficiency. Language proficiency identification is crucial while designing an EFL course as it facilitates the customization of instruction to align with learners' individual needs and abilities [24; 25; 26]. By accurately assessing learners' proficiency levels, educators can design appropriate learning objectives, select suitable instructional materials, and design relevant learning activities that cater to learners' linguistic competencies [27]. Students' language proficiency level was determined and aligned with the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) [28]. This course focuses on B1-level learners. The course targets individuals who already have a basic understanding of English and aims to enhance their language ability in grammar and vocabulary as aspects of language learning. Learning materials and activities included in the course align with learners' level to enhance learners' learning experience and outcome.

The target audience's educational background includes their previous academic experiences and qualifications. The course target audience consists of university or college students who are learning English as a Foreign Language (EFL). University students are more likely to be driven by academic and career objectives, making them eager to engage with language learning materials relevant to their future aspirations. They actively seek opportunities to improve their language skills because they understand how important language competence is to their academic performance, future employment possibilities, and general personal and career development. Hence the course is dedicated to helping such kinds of learners to reach their learning desire. The course content designed in this course is based on the learners' preferences when asked about the reason and purpose of learning English at this level.

Furthermore, university and college students are motivated by the prospect of having access to a broader range of opportunities outside of their university, such as international exchange programs in a globalized world. Therefore, designing a language course specifically tailored to the needs and aspirations of university learners ensures that the content is not only academically rigorous but also relevant,

engaging, and aligned with their long-term goals, thereby maximizing their learning experiences, and enabling them to thrive in diverse linguistic and cultural contexts.

The university and college students who participated in this study are from diverse backgrounds, but most of them are from Tanzania and Russia. These students represent a wide range of fields including education, linguistics, information technology, engineering, medicine, science, tourism, and project management. Even though these students come from different academic backgrounds and fields, their goal is to acquire vocabulary that will enable them to engage in a wide range of academic discussions rather than focusing solely on their specific fields of study. It incorporates using language for everyday academic interactions, such as discussing their courses and engaging in communication with others on and about their campus life, as well as language used for academic travel purposes.

University students often seek to broaden their experiences and perspectives, requiring them to improve their communication skills. Building a strong vocabulary is essential to communicate their ideas, and concepts, and engage in meaningful discussions within an academic setting. Additionally, proficiency in grammar is important for effective communication, enabling students to express their thoughts clearly and accurately. A solid understanding of grammar also facilitates comprehension and creation of complex academic texts and writing assignments. Furthermore, as many of these students may need to communicate with a diverse audience, such as international clients, colleagues, or patients, having a strong vocabulary and grammar skills will enable them to convey their ideas clearly and professionally. Additionally, being able to understand and use various tenses can help them accurately describe past experiences, analyze current situations, and talk about future outcomes in their academic and professional spheres.

Moreover, online courses offer learners the flexibility and independence to progress through the learning materials at their own pace. Therefore, to effectively engage in the online courses, learners need to be proficient in digital literacy skills, which allows them to navigate the online platforms and actively participate in the digital learning context. These learners are comfortable with technology and can

effectively utilize various digital tools and platforms to support their learning process. Additionally, they exhibit self-directed learning habits, taking the initiative to explore course content independently and manage their time efficiently in both synchronous and asynchronous learning settings. With their digital literacy skills, these learners demonstrate confidence in using technology to enhance their learning experience and achieve their learning goals.

As the course is online, learners are required to possess digital skills enabling them to navigate through the course and complete the required tasks. These skills include proficiency in using online learning platforms, accessing course materials, participating in virtual discussions, collaborating with peers, understanding the use of digital tools, and submitting assignments electronically on Canvas. Course target audiences demonstrate their digital literacy by engaging with various online resources and utilizing technology to support their learning journey. They exhibit comfort with technology, utilizing digital tools and platforms to explore and access instructional materials and content in the online learning setting. This adeptness with technology facilitates their ability to engage meaningfully in the digital learning environment and successfully take part in the course. Overall, learners exhibit proficiency in engaging with the course content and instructional materials, thereby demonstrating their possession of the requisite digital skills to actively participate in the designed online course.

Therefore, it is important for course designers to conduct thorough need analysis and gather relevant information about their learners, considering various factors that influence their language learning experiences. By doing this, course designers can tailor the course content, instructional techniques, and learning activities to meet the diverse needs and preferences of the students. This helps students to improve their learning experience and reach their language learning goals while ensuring that the course is engaging, interesting, relevant, and effectively contributes to their overall language development.

2.2 Needs Analysis

Needs analysis is the process of assessing the specific requirements and preferences of learners before designing a course. It involves gathering information about the learners' language proficiency, learners' needs, their prior knowledge and experiences, and their learning styles. Conducting needs analysis is crucial because it helps course developers to tailor the course content, activities, and materials to meet the learners' specific needs. By understanding target audience needs course designer can effectively determine what teaching methods and resources to employ, and how to structure the course to maximize its relevance and effectiveness.

The needs analysis process began with reviewing some official and legal documents that regulate English language teaching and learning in national and international level. The Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) [28] was analyzed to familiarize with language levels and description of each level, specifically B1 concerning skills and competencies a language learner has to master and other skills can be incorporated in a language class. The CEFR was useful to identify language skills and competencies in each level, standards, and assessment tools as it provides a comprehensive guideline concerning language levels, skills, and their description.

Additionally, legal documents were studied to identify national and international requirements and policies in English language teaching and learning in Russia and Tanzania. These documents provide insights of some regulations and standards to be followed and considered while designing a course to meet national and international standards of English language teaching. It also states appropriate instructional strategies for different kinds of learners according to their needs such as needs for learners with special needs and personalized learning.

Furthermore, the needs analysis questionnaire was used. The questionnaire was designed in a *Google* form and sent to participants online through a shared link. The questionnaires intended to gather potential learners' information, and it consisted of learners' background information, learning style, their learning

motivation, cultural aspects, preferred topics to learn, learning difficulties, and purpose of learning the language.

Needs analysis questionnaire revealed that most learners want to improve their speaking skills in the language and most of them were interested to enrich their vocabulary and improve their grammar skills. Additionally, most of them are learning English for academic and travelling purpose. The information gathered in needs analysis was used to design the course titled “Academic Mobility” focusing on grammar and vocabulary learning for communication purpose as most of the potential learners’ aim is to be able to speak and use the language in academic field and travelling.

2.3 Course Goals and Learning Objectives

The mastery of grammar and vocabulary plays a fundamental role in effective communication, enabling individuals to convey their thoughts, ideas and emotions with clarity and precision. In today’s interconnected world, proficiency in these areas in a paramount importance particularly in academic and professional contexts. This course “Academic Mobility” with a focus on grammar and vocabulary learning seeks to understand how it enhances learners’ linguistic competence, foster their communicative abilities, and empowers them to express themselves confidently and accurately in English. Through the in-depth analysis of the course content, instructional strategies, and learner outcomes this research will shed the light on how learners perceive various learning materials through blended online learning style.

In order to achieve the outcomes of this research, it is essential to outline the specific course goals and objectives. By exploring these goals and objectives in detail, we can gain a comprehensive understanding of how the course is designed to enhance learners’ language skills. Based on the finds from needs analysis from both studied documents and needs analysis questionnaire for potential learners, the following are the course goals and objectives to be achieved in this course.

The first goal is, upon successful completion of the course learners will develop understanding on the use of grammatical structures to enable them to communicate accurately and fluently in a variety of context.

Secondly, upon successful completion of the course learners will develop proper understanding in a wide range of vocabulary use in real-life situations particularly in academic context.

These goals are subsequently determined by several learning objectives which aim to fulfil learners' needs.

- by the end of the course students will be able to identify and use main verb tenses including past, present, future with its sub-forms in speaking and writing.

- by the end of the course students will be able to identify and use modal verbs while talking about their experiences.

- by the end of the course students will be able to identify grammatical and ungrammatical structures in sentences.

- by the end of the course students will be able to apply the acquired vocabulary to engage in meaningful interactions including discussions, conversations, and presentations in academic context.

- by the end of the course students will demonstrate the ability to understand and use a wide range of vocabulary to the context appropriately.

Stating course goals and learning objectives before designing the course helps to communicate and clarify the intended outcomes for both the instructor and the students. This allows for a more focused and cohesive approach for course content, material selection, and activities to enhance students leaning skills.

2.4 Assessment Tools

Assessment tools play an important role in the course as they help instructors to effectively measure and evaluate students' understanding and performance. The designed tools in this course are aligned with course objectives, allowing an instructor to assess whether students have achieved the intended learning outcomes.

These assessment tools assist an instructor to provide valuable feedback to the students on their progress and inform instructor about the effectiveness of the designed course method, content, and course materials. Employing assessment tools throughout the course enables instructors to make well – informed decisions for enhancing instructions, offer personalized assistance to students who are struggling, and provide an environment that foster ongoing learning growth among their students.

Assessment tools can take various forms, such as quizzes, exams, tests, projects, assignments, presentations, portfolios and so on. These tools help an instructor to assess different types of leaning and skills. There are a range of assessment options used to assess students' learning progress and skills in this course. Assessment tools used in this course are based on oral and written discussions, assessments which includes a variety of exercises like sentence completion, matching items, multiple-choice, quizzes, writing assignments, peer assessment and so on, oral presentations and project presentation. Assignments and quizzes are used for continuous assessment and project presentation is used for the final assessment. The total percentage for assignments is 30 %, quizzes and other learning activities such as participation, discussions, and short peer review is 50 %, tests 20 %, and the final project contains 30 %. The assignments weigh differently depending on the element is being tested, for example, quizzes weigh not more that 10 points each, written discussions weight 20 points each, other exercises weigh differently. All assessments used in this course have impact in the course accomplishment and to assess student's outcome. For students to pass the course they need to have more that 60 % on all the assessment tasks throughout the course.

In other tasks such as writing tasks, course assignments, and project have rubrics that used to grade students as shown in Table 1 and 2 below. These rubrics are embedded in the course under the specific task so that students they are aware on what is being assessed on their tasks. Other tasks to assess students' progress of the course are in form of the quiz with exact scores in each task. These quizzes are in form of multiple choice, word dropping, gap-filing, matching items, true/false,

multiple answers, and short reordering sentences. All these tasks contribute to assess learners' mastery and comprehension of the learning content and materials and check if learners are able to accomplish their leaning outcomes in this course.

Table 1 – Writing discussions rubric

Criteria	Ratings & Description			Points
	6-8	4	0-Need improvement	
Communication	A learner communicates ideas clearly and effectively -A learner responds to others' comments in a respectful and constructive manner -A learner demonstrates effective communication strategies such as asking for clarifications and contributing to discussions.	-Learners communicated ideas are unclear and partially. -Learners respond to others 'comments in a respectful manner but less constructive. -Learners fail to demonstrate effective communication strategies	A learners fail to communicate ideas clearly and effectively, does not respond to others' comments and fail to demonstrate effective communication strategies in discussions.	8
Vocabulary	-A learner uses relevant and appropriate vocabulary to express ideas effectively. -A learner uses a wide range of vocabulary appropriately and accurately in a specific context.	-A learner uses appropriate vocabulary to express ideas effectively -A learner fails to use a wide range of vocabulary appropriately and accurately in a specific context	-A learner uses limited vocabulary and fails to express themselves effectively. Inappropriate use of words and phrases in a specific context.	6
Grammar	A learner uses correct grammar structures and forms appropriately -A learner uses a wide range of sentence structures and forms appropriately and creatively -A learner demonstrates a strong command of verb tense agreement during in discussions activities.	A learner makes minor errors in grammar structures and forms appropriately -A learner uses limited sentence structures and forms -A learner demonstrates good command of verbs and tense agreement.	A learner makes consistently grammar errors that affect the ability to communicate effectively and it's difficult to understand. For example, a learner consistently uses incorrect verb tense or subject-verb agreement.	6
				Total=20

Table 2 – Project presentation rubric

Criteria	Ratings and Descriptions			Points
Content	15-Excellent	Good -11	5-fair: need improvement	20
	-A learner has communicated sufficient relevant information on the topic - Relevance and coherence of ideas.	-A learner has communicated sufficient relevant information on the topic -Relevance and coherence ideas	-Lack of coherence and relevance ideas. -Learners fail to communicate sufficient relevant information on the topic	
Organization	5	3	0	5
	-Clear introduction and conclusion -Logical sequencing of ideas -Use of transitions and examples	Clear introduction and conclusion -A learner fails to organize ideas logically and sequentially. -A learner has used some transition words and examples	Lack of clear logical and structure which can make it difficult to follow/understand Failure to use appropriate transitions which can make it difficult for others to understand the connection between ideas,	
Language skills	5	3	0	5
	-A learner uses grammar and vocabulary accurately -A learner uses were-structured and complex expressions accurately	-A learner uses limited grammatical structures and vocabulary -Occasional errors in grammar, but they don't hinder understanding of the intended content	-Poor use of grammar and vocabulary. -Multiple grammar errors and limited vocabulary, making it difficult to understand the intended content.	
Engagement	-Creativity and originality -Demonstrate engagement with the audience by using visuals and engaging tools to support a presentation.	-Creativity and originality -A learner demonstrates the use of some engaging tools to support presentation	Lack of enthusiasm/energy which can make a presentation unengaging or uninspiring	5

As shown above, these two tables contain the criteria that are used to assess students writing discussions in Table 1 and project presentation in Table 2 above. The grades are awarded based on the identified criteria and descriptions provided. Rubrics are incorporated and are open to the students in this course as it increases the fairness and transparency of the assessment process as well as help students understand expectation and areas for improvement, leading to more effective learning outcomes.

2.5 Description of Learning Activities

The learning activities in this course incorporate a diverse range of exercises and tasks to enhance learning experience and promote active participation among students. These activities are designed to actively engage students in the learning process and facilitate their understanding and application of the course material. Quizzes serve as a form of assessment to evaluate students' understanding of the material covered in the course. These quizzes are designed to test students' knowledge and comprehension of the course. The quizzes are in form of multiple-choice, gap filling, sentence completion, matching items, word order, errors correction, and short answers. Additionally, discussions both oral and written, collaborative activities are integral part of the learning process, allowing students to actively participate in the course by sharing their ideas, perspectives and opinions related to the course content. All these activities provide students with the chance to enrich their vocabulary and refine their grammar skills enabling them to communicate effectively in English language. Furthermore, assignments are given to provide students with an opportunity to apply the concepts and skills they have acquired throughout the course.

The learning activities in this course are organized based on Bloom's taxonomy, a framework that categorizes learning activities ranging from basic knowledge to more advanced thinking skills. Additionally, learning activities follow the specific algorithms according to the teaching approach used in this course which

is presentation, practice, and production. All the tasks throughout the course are arranged from lower-order thinking to higher-order thinking in order to enhance students deeper understanding of the content and materials and to enhance their overall language learning experience.

Before student delve into learning activities there is a presentation of new materials where students familiarize themselves with the learning content, then proceed to practice the materials through various activities to deepen their understanding. Most of the course learning activities follow the similar algorithm from assessing students understanding, practice the learned materials with prompts up to the point where they have free practice (without prompts). In every module there are speaking activities where learners are supposed to share their views on the provided situations to talk about while using the learned vocabulary and grammar structure for them to improve their ability to use the language in the context to enhance their communication skills.

2.6 Description of Digital Tools

The course is designed on *Canvas Instructure* and is equipped with various digital tools to elevate the learning experience and facilitate effective collaboration among students and instructor. The platform, which is *Canvas Instructure* itself has its own built-in digital tools that provide a range of functionalities. For example, discussion forum which allows students to engage in online discussions on various topics related to the course materials, assignment feature in which allows the instructor to create and distribute assignments to students, complete them and submit their work directly through the platform. Another built-in digital tool on *Canvas Instructure* includes quizzes feature which enables the instructor to design learning activities through this feature and provide feedback on students' work, collaboration forum for students and instructors to share their thoughts and ideas in the same space, and pages for instructor to design learning materials on it and be accessible to students anytime and everywhere.

In addition to the built-in tools provided by *Canvas*, other external tools are embedded within the course to further engage learners and enhance their learning experience. *Google* slides, for instance, has been incorporated for dynamic presentations, this allows students to actively interact and engage with the course materials. In addition, it allows the instructor to present concepts visually to students to strengthen their understanding of the new concepts.

Additionally, *quizlet* has been utilized as an interactive study tool for students to learn new vocabulary while having fun with this tool. Its flashcard – based system enhances vocabulary retention and promotes active learning through various study modes, including match, learn, and flashcards. This gamified approach to learning vocabulary aids in long-term retention and reinforcement of key concepts.

Moreover, *Wordwall* is employed to introduce various vocabulary – building activities into the course. This tool is embedded within modules or topics and provides a wide range of interactive games and exercises for learners to assess their knowledge on a particular topic especially in vocabulary part. Through *Wordwall* there are matching games, flashcards activities, and sentence completion that facilitate learning.

Furthermore, *Google* docs play a significant role in collaborative activities within the course in the platform. There is a *Google* doc attached to the collaboration feature on the platform where students work together on shared document, allowing them to author, edit, and comment on each other’s work. This tool promotes engagement, interaction, teamwork, communication, and the improvement of writing skills while using the learned vocabulary and grammar structures effectively and accurately.

Mind maps are also employed to organize ideas. Tools such as *coggle* has embed in this course to allow students to create colorful and interconnected diagrams to represent their thoughts and aid them in brainstorming ideas visually and share it as a means of learning from each other. Usage of different colors in *coggle* helps students to know how some concepts are connected and how are they different from each other. This tool foster creativity, improve critical thinking, and provides a

visual platform for students and instructor to organize complex information. Subsequently, there is the use of other illustrations within the courses such as images, drawings, interactive whiteboard animations, and infographics. These illustrations are strategically employed to elucidate complex concepts, providing a visual scaffolding that aids in comprehension and retention to cater diverse learning styles and contributing to a richer and more holistic learning environment.

Last but not least, *Google* slides serve as a multifaceted tool offering a dynamic, comprehensive, and visually enriched the instructional content to elevate the learning experience. Embedded *Google* slides enable the creation and delivery of visually compelling content, and it integrated texts and images to foster learning dynamics. This tool foster interaction and enables learners to actively engage with the presented materials and providing a rich and immersive learning experience. These *Google* slides are embedded on *Canvas Instructure*, and learners have full access to it for them to interact with the content materials.

2.7 Course Syllabus

The online course evaluated in this study is a 36 - hour online course organized into four modules as indicated in Table 3 below, each comprising three lessons. The delivery mode is intentionally designed to be both synchronous and asynchronous offering flexibility to cater to diverse learning preferences and schedules. On the one hand synchronous sessions provide real-time interaction and engagement, fostering immediate clarification, and facilitating dynamic discussions. Asynchronous on the other hand, allows participant to access course materials at their own pace, promoting self-directed learning. In this blended approach teacher take on the role of facilitator, guiding discussions, providing feedback, and tailoring learning resources. Students actively engage in collaborative learning activities, discussions, completing learning activities and contribute to the shared knowledge.

Table 3 – Course Syllabus

Module Number	Content
Module 1	Academic programs and courses
Module 2	Study abroad and exchange programs
Module 3	Campus life experience
Module 4	Ways of travelling

The content within each module is effectively aligned with the specified learning objectives, ensuring a successful correspondence between the course material and the intended learning outcomes. Each module is structured with seven tasks, comprising six learning activities and one main assignment or discussion, ensuring a well - rounded and participatory learning experience. Pre and post-tests serve as a benchmark, assessing students’ understanding before and after the course. Additionally, Surveys are carried out after each module to gather significant feedback for ongoing course improvement and obtaining information to investigate the main question “dynamics of material perception by students” throughout the course. Apart from the regular surveys after every module, the final survey that encompasses several questionnaires was conducted, analyzed, and reported in this paper. This comprehensive syllabus design aims to optimize learning experience, fostering a dynamic, engaging, interactive, and learner-centered environment throughout the course.

During the course, students accumulate points by actively participating in class discussions, submitting assignments, and engaging in activities tailored to the course content. The final assessment for this course is based on a pass or fail grading system, where a learner must accumulate over 60 % of the total course weigh to pass. This grading system emphasizes both active participation and a thorough understanding as essential elements to successful complete the course.

2.8 Linguistic Rationale

To justify the choice of the learning materials and instructional methods, it is important to draw upon fields of knowledge that have significantly shaped the overall structure of the course developed online. Grammar and vocabulary are important part of language learning because are essential to language competency and acquisition. In assessing the incorporation of grammar and vocabulary in second language learning and instructions it is essential to consider a variety of theories. These include theories and approaches such as second language learning, sociolinguistics, cognitive theory, language theory, communicative language teaching approach, universal grammar theory, and sociocultural theory, to mention a few. These theoretical frameworks give perspectives on language teaching and learning process, bringing multidimensional views into language learning.

Grammar provides the structural framework necessary for effective communication, while vocabulary enables learners to comprehend and express ideas effectively [29]. Besides that, [30] emphasizes the importance of grammar instruction in second language learning, stating that explicit grammar teaching helps learners internalize grammatical structures and improve their accuracy in language use. Subsequently, [31] suggested that acquiring vocabulary is essential for communicative competence and one of the central tasks for second language learners. Therefore, the process of learning the words remains the first step in acquiring any language.

Cognitive linguistics theory suggests language as a use-based events and as a component of and thus, interacting with other faculties of human cognition. These processes are laid down in communicable conceptualizations. Cognitive linguistics is characterized by a commitment to the inseparably of meaning and form in the study of language. Cognitive theory suggests that learning grammar can help students develop their cognitive abilities such as critical thinking skills. By understanding how grammar works students can improve their language comprehension and production. Cognitive linguistics views language as a tool for

communication that is shaped by the cognitive processes of the human mind. In this framework, the use of verb tenses and modal verbs is seen as a way for speakers to convey their understanding of time, possibility, and ability in language.

The designed online course takes into consideration the principle that grammar can improve students' comprehension and production. As cognitive linguistic theory suggests meaning and form are inseparable when it comes to language learning, thus the course encompasses both of them so that it can help students to learn how language form and meaning work together to help them improve their language comprehension and production. The course included the study of verb tenses and modal verbs, these structures help them to be able describe events according to the time that happens such talking about past events, present and future events. Moreover, researchers S. De Knop and T. De Rycker suggested designing a suitable Cognitive grammar approach to teaching tense and aspect, both in terms of classroom procedures and to the development of teaching and learning materials [32]. The researcher proposes a teaching approach that begins by introducing abstract concepts such as boundedness, grammatical aspect, and tense, then, a series of visual activities. This proposed structure is not different from the structure used in the course where learners are first introduced to the context to understand lexical meaning in the context, followed by the explanation of grammatical structures, then provided with the variety activities to practice their knowledge.

Furthermore, the course incorporates vocabulary learning skills in context to help students better understand and linking the words to their everyday experience. As cognitive linguistics theory based on the belief that language is influenced by our physical experiences and cognitive processes and is a result of our interaction with the world. The application of cognitive linguistics such as image schema in teaching vocabulary can enhance students' understanding and usage of English words and structure, making it a valuable and innovative method for teaching English vocabulary [33]. Hence, this approach not only facilitates language acquisition but also promotes a deeper and more meaningful connection to the language. As a result, students are able to improve their communication skills and English language

fluency. Therefore, the application of cognitive linguistics in teaching vocabulary is a valuable tool that can greatly benefit English language learners.

Moreover, the theory of second language acquisition (SLA) encompasses various perspectives on how individuals acquire language beyond their native language. One notable theory within SLA is Skill Acquisition Theory (SAT), this theory emphasizes the importance of practice and skill development in language learning. Learners acquire various skills in language including grammar and vocabulary, through exposure, practice, and feedback leading to automatization and fluency[34]. In the context of grammar and vocabulary teaching and learning, SAT suggests that learners benefit from opportunities for meaningful practice and feedback, which facilitate the internalization and mastery of linguistic structures and lexical items. Researchers have pointed out that, skill acquisition theory follow three sequential stages which are declarative, procedural, and automatization [34]. This theory suggests that for learners to be fluent and being able to communicate effectively they go through a certain procedure for them to succeed and master the target language.

The acquisition of any skill starts with declarative knowledge where a learner acquire knowledge on a learned skill. For instance, if the aim is to acquire vocabulary, then in this step a learner learns the meaning of new lexical items and their usage in context as well as recognizing common word patterns. Similarly, if the aim is to learn grammar then the learner may first learn rules and structures of the language and understand the application of those rules and structures within a sentence. In this stage learners need practical examples and abstract rules to help them smoothly move from declarative into proletarianization [34]. The knowledge acquired can then be transferred to procedural skills where the learner practices the learned skills through engaging in a variety of activities repeatedly to enhance their memory and increase proficiency. In this stage learners are expected to make mistakes, but the more they practice is the more they continue to refine their skills and become fluent in the language. The procedural skill will then lead to the automatization stage where learners can use the language fluently without much

conscious, the skill becomes automatic and effortless. Increase speed and accuracy in performing the skill characterize this stage, where both declarative and procedural skills are implemented in this stage.

The study conducted by R. Dekeyser focused on the gerund with the necessity of the integration of grammatical skills and vocabulary knowledge discovered that the most effective method for acquiring procedural skill was through massed practice [34]. This theory supports the designed online course as students they first develop the declarative knowledge through learning new lexis in the context as well grammar rules and structures. Subsequently, they participate in various exercises to reinforce the mastered skills and improve their procedural knowledge, leading to the automation of these skills. Through continued practice, they can effectively and smoothly apply these skills in real-world situations.

Another theory pertaining to second or foreign language learning is Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) approach, which focuses on developing communicative competence to students. The Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) approach is one of the most important and applicable teaching and learning theories in the contemporary language teaching profession [35; 36]. In CLT classrooms, interaction between instructor and students is vital, which also serves as a resource in the classroom. Language is used to convey meaning between participants through group and pair activities, questions and answer sessions, and evaluations [37, p. 36]. Recently, many language teachers tried to employ this approach while teaching second language to enable students apply the knowledge in their daily communication.

In contrast to traditional teaching method like grammar translation and direct method, the CLT approach focuses on student-centered and real-life language learning experiences. Most teachers tend to focus on other skills like speaking, writing, reading, and listening to improve learners' language competency. However, while grammar and lexis accuracy are not the main emphasis in speaking activities, students are able to improve their practical language skills and communication abilities through familiar and context-based learning to enhance their language

learning experiences and advancement as a whole. The teaching approach of grammar has undergone changes from a traditional way to the more innovative way where the focus is to incorporate it in the communication accuracy rather than just fluency. Additionally, [36] suggested that for the development of communicative ability research findings overwhelmingly support the integration of form – focused exercises with meaning – focused experience.

By incorporating accuracy and grammar correction into Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), both fluency and accuracy can be achieved simultaneously. The ultimate goal of this approach is to improve students' communicative competence in the language by providing them with the tools that can help them to communicate effectively in the real-life situations [38].

The recent studies found out that English learners demonstrate significant errors in areas such as tense, grammatical agreement, case, and other facets of language structures in both formative and summative assessments [39, p. 20]. This approach suggests that grammatical structures should be taught within a meaningful and appropriate context for the grammatical concept to be retained and applied in a meaningful context while engaging in a maximum interaction. Verb tense comprehension is essential for students to understand the text level. Understanding a particular verb phrase impacts comprehension at the sentence, paragraph and ultimately at the discourse level. Hence, students need to understand grammatical structures which appropriately suit the audience and purpose of communication. For instance, understanding how verb tenses are used, students can share their meaningful past experiences, present, and future predictions on various situations.

Since the main focus of CTL approach is on communication, including vocabulary and grammar instruction in the designed course helps students improve their practical language skills and communication abilities. By integrating activities that focus on language form with meaning-form experiences that emphasize real-life relevance, students can enhance their ability to communicate effectively in various academic and personal situations. For example, using appropriate verb tenses they can share their past and or present situations as well as talk about their future plans

and predictions using vocabulary previously introduced. This helps them to broaden their understanding and effectively apply the language in context to facilitate their communication skills and retention of the language structure for meaningful use. This approach enables them to articulate their experiences at different stages of their academic lives with greater fluency and accuracy by using the appropriate verb tenses in communication.

Furthermore, another theory that underlines the intergradation of grammar in the course is universal grammar proposed by a linguist Noam Chomsky. According to this theory, all human languages share a common underlying structure or set of principles that govern the way language is learned and used. This includes the use of verb tenses to indicate the time of an action or events that are covered in the course. Universal grammar theory guide learners to identify the grammatical and ungrammatical structures in a language. In several instances, the language comprehension extends beyond the input. For instance, both children and adults have the ability to understand and produce sentences they have never been exposed to before, distinguish between grammatically correct and incorrect structures intuitively, and recognize when certain interpretations of sentences are not appropriate in certain situations [40, p. 34; 41]. While this theory plays a significant role understanding grammar rules and helps students to determine grammatical and ungrammatical structures, this study also incorporates the evaluation of the correct and incorrect structures through grammaticality judgement test, which helps in evaluating the accuracy of sentence structures.

Universal grammar features allow us to establish a foundation for generalization beyond our initial experiences. By encountering different linguistic forms and structures, we are able to identify patterns and representations that help us understand and learn new grammar rules while inferring to our past and real-life experiences. In universal grammar theory learners receive input and generalize them to produce a meaningful output. Hence, for them to produce that meaningful output they need to have a solid understanding of the rules and structure of the target language.

To sum up, the designed online course integrates the study of grammar and vocabulary can be explained through a range of linguistic theories, including universal grammar, communicative language instruction, second language acquisition, and cognitive linguistics. These theories place a strong emphasis on the value of communicative ability, skill acquisition, context-based learning, and an underlying universal structures in language learning. Course designers can successfully enhance their students' language comprehension, production, and communication abilities by taking into consideration various theories and approaches that provides learned with significant learning experience and achieve the desired learning outcomes.

3 Learners' Performance Analysis

This chapter provides course trial phase analysis and learners' engagement evaluation during the course probation period. This section includes description of the course trial, analysis, reports the results, and interpretation of the results from the collected data drawing from the theoretical framework discussed in earlier chapters. The analysis is followed by recommendations for enhancing the course including learning materials, delivery format, methodologies, and organization of the learning process.

3.1 Description of the Course Trial

The designed online course "Academic Mobility" focused on grammar and Vocabulary learning within the curriculum was launched in November 2023 and ended in March 2024. The course was delivered through asynchronous and synchronous format (bichronous). It is substantiated by the fact that the course created was supported by the findings of needs analysis conducted before the course design process began. The course goals, learning objectives, learning materials, and course content were also developed based on the needs analysis findings. Moreover, the needs analysis was a crucial step in understanding learners' learning style and their language proficiency, which informed the design of the course. By identifying their language styles and preferences for language skills, we were able to tailor the course content and delivery to better meet needs and maximize learning outcomes. This ensured that the course is relevant, engaging, interactive, and effective for the learners. The course consists of four modules and the completion of the presented modules requires about 36 hours in total.

The materials were crafted in accordance with the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) English levels, adhering to the proficiency standards outlined by the CEFR. This approach ensured that the course content and materials were designed to suit the linguistic competencies and learning objectives

corresponding to specific CEFR proficiency levels. By aligning with the CEFR framework, the materials aimed to provide a systematic and structured approach to language learning, facilitating learners' progress and skills development within the established CEFR proficiency levels. According to the CEFR framework the course content and materials designed align with B1 English proficiency level.

The participants enrolled to the course on *Canvas Instructure* through the provided link. Before the course started at least seven members were already joined the course, and three members joined the course later making the total of ten students who registered to take part in the course trial phase. However, out of the ten participants who initially registered for the course, only seven were able to successfully complete it as three participants become absolutely inactive after the mid-course evaluation as shown in Figure 1 below. Despite being university and college students, the participation of the enrolled students in the course was notably inadequate. This lack of engagement was primarily attributed to the demanding nature of their academic responsibilities, leading to difficulties in attending scheduled online meetings and actively participating in course activities. Despite offering students with a range of flexible meeting times to accommodate their schedules, they were unwilling to suggest the suitable options for them resulting in the inability to schedule the planned online sessions for all throughout the trial period of the course. Only one student was able to suggest the time and conduct the online session. This lack of proactive engagement from the students led to the unfortunate consequence of not being able to conduct the planned synchronous virtual meetings during the trial phase. Consequently, the limited involvement of students in online activities and discussions posed significant challenges to the efficacy of the learning experience, thereby impeding their comprehensive engagement with the course content, learning objectives and materials throughout the trial period.

Figure 1 – The ratio between course enrollment and course completion

In addition to the online engagement, data collection encompassed pre and post-tests administered. The pre-test was conducted prior the course trial and the post-test were carried out at the end of the course trial phase (the results is reported in the following part 3.2). However, regardless of the limited online participation, students displayed a proactive attitude by actively participating in and completing both the pre and post-tests. To further gauge student perceptions of the course materials, a comprehensive survey was disseminated to students via *Google* forms, offering them the opportunity to provide feedback and perspective about the course. Their completion of the survey facilitated a deeper understanding of their perspectives on the course materials and learning experience.

In the survey conducted after the course trial, the participants were asked to rate the course trial duration. This question aimed to investigate whether the participants are satisfied with the time were given to complete the course since was launched. The figure below shows the results regarding the time for the course trial. The question asked is “How would you rate the overall course duration since it was launched?”

Figure 2 – Students’ perspectives on the course trial period

As shown in Figure 2 above, the result revealed that time for the course trial was right as all participants indicates that. This means that participants had the enough time to complete the course including learning activities that aimed to help learners to assess their own progress in the course.

However, the participants were asked to share some challenges they faced during the course trial period that impeded them not to complete all the tasks in the course for some students. The figure below shows the students point of view regarding this matter.

Figure 3 – Challenges students faced during the course trial period

Among the students who stayed and kept participating in the course until the time of the course trial phase ended, most of them could not complete all the tasks included in the course. Hence they were asked to share the challenges they faced that resulted them not to complete all the activities. As shown in Figure 3 above, students provided different views on the challenges they faced during the course trial phase. Subsequently, these challenges impeded some students not to finish all the activities included in the course. Even though students did not complete all the tasks, but they were able to complete more than half of the activities, especially those designed in quizzes format

3.2 Results and Data Interpretation of the course Trial.

This part of the paper is dedicated to report the results of the study responding to two research questions mentioned before which are:

- How do students perceive various digital learning materials in an online learning environment?

– To what extent does the course impact student's grammar and vocabulary skills?

The study employed *JASP statistical analysis software* and *Microsoft Excel* for data analysis. The study focused on two distinct research questions, each of which required different analytical approaches. The first question examined students' perceptions of the course materials and was analyzed using *Microsoft Excel* to assess their dynamics. Conversely, the second question investigated how the online course impact students' grammar and vocabulary skills, which was analyzed using the *JASP (Jeffreys's Amazing Statistics Program) statistical analysis software*.

To address the first research question, the questionnaire was sent to the students through *Google form* and responded to it. The data derived from the questionnaire were analyzed and scored automatically in *Microsoft Excel* in all question items. The study used a mixed method to investigate the course material perceptions of the students who have attended the course. The students were provided with the survey questionnaire to complete. The statements and questions were designed in a Likert scale survey with 3-scale points: 'Agree', 'Neither Agree nor Disagree', and 'Disagree'. The students were asked to choose the option that describes their learning experiences and preferences in the course. The analysis of the response was done as shown in the graphs below. More information about the materials used during the study are available in the Appendix section.

Figure 4 below shows the results to the statements which aimed to assess what kind of learning materials students prefer.

Figure 4 – Students’ preferences and perceptions on the course materials used in the designed online course

According to the survey conducted at the end of the course trial, six out of seven respondents agree that they prefer to access content in the form of PowerPoint, while one respondent disagrees with that form of accessing material content. Regarding watching videos, six respondents agree, while one respondent disagrees. Additionally, results revealed that, six out of seven respondents neither agree nor disagree with listening to the audio files posted into the course. Furthermore, four respondents agree and prefer when concepts are illustrated using mind maps, images, and presented in a format of reading text, while three of them neither agree nor disagree with the statements.

Based on these results, the findings suggest that the majority of respondents prefer accessing content in the form of PowerPoint presentations and watching videos. When it comes to presenting concepts, there is a slight preference for using mind maps, images, and reading text, while others are neutral on this approach. However, six students remained neutral when it comes to listening to audio files, as most respondents neither agree nor disagree with this form of materials. Ultimately,

it appears that visuals, audiovisuals, and interactive form of content are generally more preferred by the respondents.

Figure 5 below shows the results for the questions which aimed to assess how students perceive course content organization and effectiveness, whether the materials are clear and easy to understand, relevance of the course materials, whether the course materials are relevant and engaging, and the overall impression of the course.

Figure 5 – Students’ perceptions of course material content and organization

As shown in Figure 5 above, most of the participants agreed on the statements on the survey based on the course materials, content, and organization. Based on the results, six participants out of seven who took part in the survey find the course to be well organized, engaging, and relevant. They acknowledged the clarity and ease

of navigation of the course materials, as well as how they are organized in a logical and coherent manner. Additionally, participants find the learning activities, such as quizzes, to enhance their learning experience. Overall, these results indicate that the course design materials and content are effective in meeting the participants’ needs and their learning expectations.

Moreover, to further assess students’ perspectives in the online course materials, the participants were asked to rate how helpful were the course materials format to facilitate their learning experience during the course trial period. Figure 6 below shows the results obtained from the students.

Figure 6 – Students’ perceptions of the course materials delivery format on the online course

Based on the results, all participants found the videos to be very helpful in enhancing their understanding of the content. The audios were split, with two finding them extremely and moderately helpful respectively, while three finding them slightly helpful, and none finding them not helpful. The mind maps were rated as

moderately helpful by five respondents, slightly helpful by one, and very helpful by one, and no one rated them not helpful. The images in the course were rated moderately by four respondents, while two of them finding them very helpful, and one finding them slightly helpful.

Overall, it seems that the videos were the most helpful in enhancing the understanding of the content for the majority of respondents. The audios were also generally viewed positively, with a mix of responses indicating different levels of helpfulness. Mind maps were considered moderately helpful by most respondents, but there was also a significant number who found them very helpful. The images in the course were not rated as highly overall, with most respondents finding them moderately helpful. Hence, it appears that the use of multimedia elements such as videos, audios, mind maps, and images could be beneficial in enhancing the understanding of the content for the majority of the online students.

On top of that, there are further questions included in the survey to assess other aspects of the course in relation to the course materials. The Figure 7 below displays the finds of students' perspectives on how the course materials were engaging and interactive to enhance their learning experience.

Figure 7 – Interactivity of the course materials

As shown in the figure above, the finds revealed that all participative of the course perceived the course materials as interactive and engaging to enhance their learning experience.

Figure 8 – Quality of the course materials in alignment with the learning objectives

To further explore students’ perspectives on the course materials, participants were asked to evaluate the quality of the materials in alignment with the learning objectives. The findings indicated that six respondents found the materials perfectly suitable, one respondent rated them as highly suitable, while none considered the materials moderately, somewhat, or not suitable in accordance with the stated learning objectives of the course as shown in Figure 8 above. Overall, the results suggests that the course materials effectively aligned with the specified learning objectives, as indicated by the majority of participants rating them as suitable or highly suitable. This alignment likely contributed to the positive perception of the materials by the students.

Furthermore, the students were asked to assess whether the course materials were relevant and applicable to their real-life scenarios. Figure 9 shows the findings.

Figure 9 – Students’ perceptions on the relevance and applicability of the of the course materials

The findings revealed that all respondents agreed that the course materials were highly relevant and applicable to their real-life scenarios. This results suggests that the materials effectively address practical aspects and are perceived as directly applicable to the participants’ everyday experiences.

In this study, participants were also asked to provide their satisfaction on the alignment between the instructional materials and the course content of the online course. The findings regarding this aspect are illustrated in Figure 10 below.

Figure 10 – Students’ satisfaction with the course content in relation to instructional materials

As shown in figure 10 above, six respondents expressed high satisfaction, one respondent expressed satisfaction, and none of the participants were neutral or dissatisfied with the content presented in the course. This suggests a strong relationship between the course content and the materials provided, indicating that the instructional resources effectively aligned with the subject matter covered in the blended online course.

To address the second question, two versions of tests were used in this study, namely the Grammaticality Judgement Test (GJT) and the vocabulary test. These tests aimed to assess the student's proficiency in both grammar and vocabulary. The data were computed and analyzed through the use of *JASP statistical analysis* software, which included the implementation of a T-test method.

Grammaticality Judgement Test.

To answer the second question in GJT, the Shapiro-Wilk test was used because the number of the participants was less than 50. The Shapiro-Wilk test showed that the variable in the pre-test was normally distributed ($p = 0.248$); therefore, the parametric t-test was used in the analysis. On the other hand, the variable in the post-test was not normally distributed ($p < .001$) as shown in table 4 below. Therefore, a non-parametric t-test was used in the analysis.

Table 4 – Descriptive Statistics

	pre-test	post-test
valid	7	7
Missing	0	0
Mean	21.00	24. 857
Std. deviation	2.944	0. 378
Shapiro-Wilk	0.885	0.453
P-value of Shapiro-Wilk	0.389	< .001
Minimum	16.000	24.00
Maximum	24.000	25.00

A paired sample t-test in the parametric test for the pre-test showed the increase of scores to be significant ($t(6) = -3.652, p = 0.011$) as shown in Table 5 below. In this test, the result showed a statistically significant difference between the two tests with a p-value of less than 0.05. This indicates that there is a significant increase in scores from the pre-test to the post-test. However, A Wilcoxon's signed-rank test in the pre-test revealed that ($W = 28.000, p = 0.022$) as shown in Table 6. Based on the given results, it is appropriate to say that there is a statistically significant difference in scores between two tests as there is an increase in scores from the pre-test to the post-test, and this increase is statistically significant.

Table 5 – Paired Samples Parametric T-Test

Measure 1		Measure 2	t	df	p
Pre-test	-	Post-test	-3.652	6	0.011

Note – Student's t-test

Table 6 – Paired Samples non-parametric T-Test

Measure 1		Measure 2	W	df	p
Pre-test	-	Post-test	28.000		0.022

Note – Wilcoxon signed-rank test

Table 5 shows the statistical results obtained from parametric- test while Table 6 shows the paired samples of the non-parametric test.

Furthermore, the analysis revealed that, the mean of the post-test (mean = 24.857) was significantly higher than the mean of the pre-test (mean = 21.000) as shown in Table 7 below. These finds suggest that there may be a meaningful relationship between the tests being compared. Ultimately, based on this result, it indicates that overall participants improved their grammar knowledge and skills after the course.

Table 7 – Samples mean

	N	Mean	SD	SE
Pre- test	7	21.000	2.944	1.113
Post-test	7	24.857	0.378	0.143

As shown in Table 6 and 7 above, the mean from post-test is higher than the mean from the pre-test. Hence, this suggest that the course helped students to improve their grammar skills after the course completion.

Vocabulary test.

Furthermore, to answer the first question to what extent the course impacted students' vocabulary skills, the analysis was run in *JASP*. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used because the number of participants was less than 50 students. The Shapiro-Wilk test revealed that the variable in the pre-test was normally distributed ($p = 0.262$); therefore, the parametric t-test was used in the analysis. On the other hand, the variable in the post-test was not normally distributed ($p < .001$) as shown in Table 8 below. Therefore, a non-parametric t-test was used in the analysis.

Table 8 – Descriptive Statistics

	pre-test	post test
valid	7	7
Missing	0	0
Mean	12.571	14.714
Std. deviation	1.134	0.488
Shapiro-Wilk	0.887	0.600
P-value of Shapiro-Wilk	0.262	<.001
Minimum	11.000	14.00
Maximum	14.000	15.00

A paired sample t-test in the parametric test for the pre-test showed the increase of scores to be significant ($t(6) = -4.666$, $p = 0.003$) as shown in Table 9 below. In this test, the result showed a statistically significant difference between the two tests with a p-value of less than 0.05. This indicates that there is a significant increase in scores from the pre-test to the post-test. However, A Wilcoxon's signed-rank test in the pre-test revealed that ($W = 28.000$, $p = 0.021$) as shown in Table 10.

Based on the given results, it is appropriate to say that there is a statistically significant difference in scores between two tests as there is an increase in scores from the pre-test to the post-test, and this increase is statistically significant.

Table 9 – Paired Samples parametric T-Test

Measure 1		Measure 2	t	df	p
Pre-test	-	Post-test	-4.666	6	0.003

Note – Student's t-test

Table 10 – Paired samples non-parametric T-Test

Measure 1		Measure 2	W	df	p
Pre-test	-	Post-test	28.000		0.021

Note – Wilcoxon signed-rank test

The results in Table 9 indicate that there is a statistical difference between pre-test and post-test scores, with a p-value of less than 0.05. Also, Table 10 shows that the non-parametric test revealed significant improvement in test scores from pre-test to post-test with a p-value 0.021 which is less than 0.05.

In addition, the analysis showed that, the mean of the post-test (mean = 14.714) was significantly higher than the mean of the pre-test (mean = 12.571) as shown in table 11 below. These finds suggest that there may be a meaningful relationship between the tests being compared. Generally, based on this result, it indicates that overall participants improved their vocabulary knowledge and skills after the course completion.

Table 11 – Samples mean

	N	Mean	SD	SE
Pre- test	7	12.571	1.134	0.429
Post-test	7	14.714	0.488	0.184

According to Table 11, the statistical difference in mean from pre-test to post-test proves that the students were able to improve their vocabulary skills after the course.

3.3 Recommendations for the Course Improvement.

The comprehensive evaluation of the course trial results revealed valuable insights that must be carefully considered. Based on the analysis of the course trial phase several key areas of improvement have been identified to enhance the effectiveness of the course. By implementing these recommendations, the course efficiency can be optimized, fostering an engaging and inclusive online learning environment that maximizes students' language learning and overall course performance.

One of the significant recommendations pertains to the implementation of blended learning. The course was originally designed to be delivered through a combination of asynchronous and synchronous instruction in a virtual setting. Based on the needs analysis conducted prior to the course design and execution, students suggested incorporating virtual online lessons to enhance their learning experience. This would allow them to practice their skills with fellow students and interact with the teacher in order to maximize their learning experience. However, throughout the time of the course trial phase there was only one successfully virtual meeting with one student. Most students claim the reason is because of time differences, others could not join on the virtual meetings due to the other commitments outside the course and internet problems.

Given this challenge of the blended learning approach to address the concerns raised by students is to consider offering the course exclusively through asynchronous learning approach, unless the instructor is certain that all students are able and willing to participate in scheduled virtual meetings. This may include providing recorded lectures, discussion boards, or collaborative projects with flexible deadlines to ensure that all students have access to course materials and activities regardless of their availability. Additionally, for the students to practice their skills such as applying the learned skills in speaking, they can be provided with the tool that enables them to record their voice and send to the instructor for the evaluation. Ultimately, while blended learning offers numerous benefits in terms of flexibility and engagement, it is essential to address challenges such as time differences and external factors to optimize the learning experience for all participants.

In addition, minimal student involvement and participation were observed during the course trial phase. This resulted to some of the students not being able to complete the course. Despite efforts put into creating interactive and engaging learning activities throughout the course, facilitating collaboration for students to share their ideas in a collaboration page, maintaining constant communication with them, and motivating them to actively engage in the course, it is evident that additional approaches are necessary to encourage students to actively participate and engage to the course.

One strategy that has been suggested to increase students' motivation and participation in online learning courses, where participation is voluntary, is to incorporate gamification elements into the course design, such as interactive quizzes with leaderboards, achievement badges for completing tasks, or virtual rewards for active participation. Gamification has been shown to enhance motivation and engagement in various educational contexts by leveraging elements of competition, achievement, and reward to incentivize learning [42]. As learners are from different places around the world and this course it is not part of their main courses, hence it is challenging for them to fully commit to the course. Some of them may have

intrinsic motivation and some may have extrinsic motivation, but their motivation needs to be fostered in order for them to continue learning. Hence, implementing gamification approach and rewards might elevate their motivation and impact their learning experience positively.

The course consists of four modules that cover vocabulary and grammar. Each module constitutes six to eight tasks arranged following Bloom's taxonomy level of learning. All the activities on the course are meant to enhance students' language skills learning and providing them with an opportunity to practice the application of the language skills in a broader context to reinforce their language proficiency and fluency. Incorporating more practice activities in the course can also facilitate students' understanding, promote active learning as well as further their skills development. However, some students claim there are many tasks in the designed course, hence they requested to reduce the number of the practice activities.

Therefore, for improving the course and ensuring that students stay engaged and motivated throughout the course there is a need to reduce the number of activities by prioritizing quality tasks over quantity. Alternatively, the instructor can provide clear instructions and rationale behind those activities in the course and how they play a key role to their learning holistically. With meaningful rationale and clear instructions, learners can understand the relevance of those activities and remain focused throughout the course.

Generally, while developing an online course in this dynamic online learning environment it is challenging to know and understand what learners need and consider as an effective and impactful course. Hence, the aforementioned recommendations aim to provide an overview of the course improvement, aiming to improve course effectiveness and the overall students' learning experience. Gathering timely feedback from students may help the course designer to make improvements in the course that can optimize students' learning experience and improve their overall learning outcomes. For the further improvement of the course, there is a need to reconsider these suggestions and modify the course accordingly to make it more effective.

Conclusion

Learning materials play a significant role in the teaching and learning process. These materials consist of learning activities, content, samples, topic materials, assessment, multimedia instructional materials such as videos, audios, visuals, texts, and other instructional materials. These learning materials should accelerate students' learning achievements, helping students to achieve learning goals and improve their performance. Moreover, learning material sources do not only come from books, but course developers can adopt, adapt, add, modify, and narrow learning materials from various available learning sources to meet students' needs and achieve their course goals and learning objectives [43].

This study aimed to investigate the dynamics of students' material perception in a blended online learning environment and examine how has it impacted students' language skills development, seeking to contribute to the existing studies on digital learning. The study data gathered involved a detailed examination of students' grammatical and vocabulary skills, coupled with an investigation into their perceptions of various digital learning materials. The study information and data analysis based on the online course developed on *Canvas Instructure*. The findings gathered through a survey questionnaire, provided a comprehensive understanding of the subject.

The study process involved planning and organizing important information from the students before designing the course. The need analysis was carried out through questionnaires and from necessary documents that regulate education, particularly in learning English language at the national and international level. Need analysis aimed to gather information about learners needs, behaviors, their background experience and learning styles, as well as standards need to be considered while designing the course. Needs analysis resulted to the formulation of course goals, learning objectives, syllabus, and other necessary course elements.

Following the needs analysis, the online course was developed. Learning materials were tailored to suit learners needs and their learning goals. The course

entitled a variety of learning materials that were developed using various digital tools to facilitate interactivity and engagement. After the course development phase, the course was piloted, and students were given an opportunity to participate and engage to the course in an online learning environment. The results were collected, analyzed, interpreted, and reported as shown in this paper.

Based on the findings above, on material perception, assessed through the questionnaire, revealed strong preferences among students. The majority favored illustrated text materials, especially in formats of PowerPoint, MS Word, and PDF. Videos were also well-received, while audio files materials were the least preferred materials. These findings do not contradict much with the previous studies such as [8]. Furthermore, mind maps, images, and reading texts were preferred after videos and illustrated texts materials. Overall, the findings suggest a diverse preference for multimedia instructional materials, emphasizing the importance of tailored approaches in course design.

Additionally, to further gather more information on how students perceive materials in online settings, the survey evaluated the course content materials and organization. Findings indicated that the course content materials were perceived positively by the majority of students, who found them relevant, high quality, engaging, interactive, clear, and easy to understand as well as logical and organized in coherent manner. This means that while designing an online course it is important for developers to ensure they tailor the content materials that foster positive learning environment to the students. Taking into consideration these factors can provide learners with a meaningful learning experience and ultimately improve their learning outcomes. These factors provide a thorough picture of how the materials affect participants to remain motivated, engaged and interested into the course they pursue.

The findings of whether the course impacted student's grammar and vocabulary skills were also reported in this study. The results revealed the significant increase in scores from the pre-test to the post-test, as indicated by both parametric and non-parametric tests, suggests that participants improved their grammar

knowledge and skills after taking the course. This suggests that the course positively influenced the participants' comprehension of grammar. The vocabulary test results, as the GJT, show a significant improvement in both parametric and non-parametric tests, suggesting that the course greatly improved the participants' vocabulary skills. The outcomes from both the Grammaticality Judgment Test (GJT) and Vocabulary assessment demonstrate a statistically significant and positive impact of the course on the participants, enhancing their proficiency in vocabulary and grammatical knowledge. These results support the effectiveness of the learning materials used in the course.

Overall, online learning has a significant impact and contribution to today's world as students can enhance and improve their skills using these courses. Hence, to ensure the effectiveness and relevance of these courses it is essential for course developers to consider student perspectives. Gathering more information and viewpoints of students concerning online learning environment can help course developers to tailor and deliver the course materials and content that are relevant and suitable to the target audience.

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Needs Analysis Questionnaire

Table A.1 – Needs Analysis Questionnaire

QUESTION	0= Never	1= Not often	2= sometimes	3= often	4= Always
I prefer working individually than in a group					
Do you prefer working with others in a group					
I prefer using colors, create tables, mind maps, and chats to organize my note					
I enjoy listening to a music or songs in a classroom					
I would rather listen to a good lecture/speech than reading about the same materials in the textbook					
How often do you write while reading					
I prefer to learn with TV or videos rather than other type of media					
I prefer activities that involve movements, and making things with my hands or activities that require me to do things on my own					
I need written direction or tasks					
I need frequent break when I do tasks or study					
I prefer discussions more when we are in the class					
I like to discover things on myself rather than having everything explained to me					
I prefer challenging activities					
I prefer lectures more compared to interactions/discussions in the classroom					
When I am in a large group I tend to keep silent and listen					
I prefer things presented in a step-by-step way					
I have to look to people to understand what they say					
I enjoy games while learning					
I enjoy learning language grammar					
I can use variety of vocabulary talking about one thing while speaking					
I have difficulties in understanding verbal communication, it is difficult for me to understand a message delivered when someone is speaking					

Appendix B

Pre- and Post-tests Grammar Questions

Grammaticality Judgement Test (GJT)

Instruction: Pick one correct grammatical structure from the two options you have given

Each question weigh one point

Past Tense

1. He attends a prestigious university for his master's program
He attended a prestigious university for his master's program
2. The campus life was exciting during their time there
The campus life was excited during their time there
3. By the time she arrived, the lecture had already started
By the time she arrived, the lecture has already started
4. They had been worked on their science project for hours
They had been working on their science project for hours
5. The students were taking notes during the lecture
The students was taking notes during the lecture

Present Tense

1. They regularly attends classes
They regularly attend classes
2. They travelling to different countries this summer
They are travelling to different countries this summer
3. The professor has been teaching this course for years
The professor have been taught this course for years
4. They have been participated in the exchange programs recently

They have been participating in the exchange program recently

5. She prefers to live around the campus rather than at home
She prefer to live around the campus rather than at home

Future Tense

1. He will enrol in advanced courses next semester
He enrol in advanced courses next semester
2. The students takes part in the language exchange program abroad
The students will take part in the study abroad program
3. They will travelled during the summer break
They will be travelling during the summer break
4. We will travels to different countries next year
We will travel to different countries next year
5. I graduates in two years
I will graduate in two years

Going to

1. They is going to be studying computer science next semester
They are going to study computer science next semester
2. The participants are going to stay with the host family
The participants are going to staying with the host family
3. She going to attend the cultural fair in the campus next week
She is going to attend the cultural fair in the campus next week
4. My friend is going to take part in the extensive language course next summer
My friend is going talking part in the extensive language course next summer

5. By next month, Alex and Alen are going to attend conferences on behalf of the students' organization

By next months, Alex and Alen is going to attend the conference on behalf of the students' organization

Modal Verbs

1. We could have enjoyed the local festival by attending the cultural activities that happened during our visit to Thailand

We can have enjoyed the local festival by attending the cultural activities that happened during our visit to Thailand

2. In summer, you might encounter occasional rain showers during your outdoor activities
In summer, you may encounter occasional rain showers during your outdoor activities

3. If you are well-prepared, you could pack for a weekend road trip in no time
If you are well-prepared, you can pack for a weekend road trip in no time

4. Even with the limited budget, we managed to travel to our dream destination by the flight
Even with the limited budget, we managed to travelled to our dream destination by the flight

5. They were so tired that they can't stay awake during the long bus ride
They were so tired that they couldn't stay awake during the long bus ride.

Appendix C

Pre- and Post-tests Vocabulary Questions

Choose the word from the drop list below to match with its definition

Table C.1 – Vocabulary Questions

	Definition	Drop list words
1	A formal talk on a subject given to a group of students	Options - Dedication - Thrive - Lecture - Library - Exploration - Scholarship - Graduation - Adaptation - Facilities - Orientation - Campus - extra- curricular activities - immersion - Dormitory - Assignments
2	Tasks that you do for a course completion	
3	Activities that you do after main classes has ended for fun or to learn something new out of class such as sports, clubs, etc	
4	The place where college/school/university is located	
5	A place where students live together on a collage / campus	
6	The commitment and effort put into doing something	
7	The process of adjusting to a new environment or culture	
8	The complete involvement in or deep engagement with a particular activity or culture	
9	The act of exploring or investigating new places or ideas	
10	Financial support given to students to help cover the costs of studying	
11	Buildings or spaces on campus such as laboratories, play grounds, computer rooms, or study areas, library etc	
12	The ceremony marking the completion of studies and the awarding of degrees	
13	A program or event to introduce new students to campus life	
14	A place where students can access books or study materials	
15	To do really well, grow and be successful and continue to exist.	